

72) *Addenda à Nanna O (NABU 2001/41)* – J'ai remarqué malheureusement trop tard que J. Krecher et J. Klein (*TAPS* 71 [1981] 42) avaient déjà relevé et discuté le parallélisme entre Nanna O rev. 3'-10', *VS* 2 4 rev. ii 39-iii 5 et Inana I 22'-25'. Qu'ils trouvent ici l'expression de mes excuses pour cette omission.

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73) *Assyrian Merchants at Dūr-Kurigalzu* – B. Faist in *Der Fernhandel des assyrischen Reiches zwischen dem 14. und 11. Jh. v. Chr.*, p. 167 transliterates from a photograph ten lines of a tablet from Dūr-Kurigalzu, IM 49992 (=DK₃-9), marking with asterisks twenty-one sign readings which she considered doubtful. I examined this tablet in Baghdad some years ago and can offer the following confirmations, corrections, and additions to her edition.

- (26) 7 ME 33 TÚG.SÍG ZI.GA *i-na lib-bi*
 (27) NÍG.GA URU BÀD-*Ku-ri-gal-zu*
 (28) ša ŠU ¹Ri-mut-^dBa-ba₆
 (29) ù ^dUTU-SUM-MU DU[B.S]AR.MEŠ
 (30) *a-na* DAM.GÀR.MEŠ DUMU.MEŠ *aš-šur-a-a-i*
 (31) ¹Mu-un-na-bit-t[u?]
 (32) EN.NAM *id-di-i[n]*

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- (33) URU BÀD-*Ku-ri-gal-zu*
 (34) ITI.APIN U₄.15?.KÁM MU.3.KÁM.2? ¹KÁM
 (35) ^dAMAR.UTU-IBILA-SUM-*na* LUGAL.E
 (36) NA₄.KIŠIB ¹Mu-un-na-bit-ti
 (37) EN.NAM

Notes on line 34: the reading of the day number as given here seems most likely, but there are possibly traces of another 10, probably erased; the second ordinal number in the year date has one vertical wedge definitely visible, but spacing suggests that 2 is the preferable reading here (which would make the number comparable to MU.1.KÁM.2.KÁM in IM 50023; see below).

The scribes Rīmūt-Baba and Šamaš-nādin-šumi are attested in other texts in the Dūr-Kurigalzu archives. They occur together with the same Munnabittu in IM 50025 (DK₃-11), another tablet dealing with the issue of woollen textiles from the palace holdings at Dūr-Kurigalzu; this text is dated at Babylon on II-25-year 6 of Marduk-apla-iddina I (1171-1159). These scribes are also involved in another similar issue of woollen textiles from Dūr-Kurigalzu, this time under the supervision of Šamaš-bēl-ilī, governor of Dūr-Kurigalzu (with the title *šaknu*, here written GAR-*in* GN); this text, IM 50023 (DK₃-8), edited by Gurney in *Iraq* 11 (1949) 137 and 146 no. 7, is dated XI-^d41-MU.1.KÁM.2.KÁM in the reign of Marduk-apla-iddina I. These three tablets appear in a photograph which was published in *Iraq*, Supplement 1945, pl. XXII and in *Sumer* 1/1 (Jan. 1945) pl. 7 following p. 72 of the Arabic section.

These three tablets, reportedly blackened by fire associated with a burning of the palace possibly at the time of the collapse of the dynasty a few years later, were found with five further tablets or fragments in the palace at Tell al-'Abyaḍ at the entrance to room 2 in level IA, close to chambers 12, 13, and 14, each of which has twelve or more small vaulted recesses in its walls. These have sometimes been interpreted as storage magazines; see *Iraq*, Supplement 1945, pp. 5-6 (description), pl. VI (location of the chambers in level I), pl. XVI (plan and section of room 12), and pls. XIII, XIV, XVII (photos showing the vaulted recesses and adjacent architectural features). Level IA is the latest preserved Kassite level of the palace. It is unknown whether there were further similar chambers beyond room 14 to the south-southeast because excavation stopped at that point. Margueron points out that use of these rooms for the handling of merchandise would have been awkward and, if the rooms were so utilized, such usage would have been secondary and not originally intended (*Recherches sur les palais mésopotamiens de l'Age du Bronze*, I, 458).

It is also worth mentioning that an Assyrian (LÚ *aš-šur-ú*) whose personal name is damaged on the tablet is documented as the recipient of woollen garments in another of the texts found in the same locus and referring to material given out from the stores of Dūr-Kurigalzu (IM 50088 = DK₃-6, rev. 5, date not preserved).

Double-numbered year dates, attested thus far only for the reigns of Adad-šuma-ušur, Meli-Šipak, and Marduk-apla-iddina I in the late thirteenth and early twelfth centuries, are discussed in my *Materials and Studies for Kassite History*, vol. 1, pp. 410-411. See especially *ibid.*, n. 54 where the Dūr-Kurigalzu double-numbered year dates and scribal personnel are discussed; but note that the month given there for the date in IM 50025 should be corrected to «II» rather than «V» (given correctly *ibid.*, p. 250)

One should also lay to rest the notion that these garments or textiles were «received or distributed on